

Resident Evil 7: Biohazard Review

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GAME INFO

- **ORIGINAL TITLE:** *BIOHAZARD 7 – Resident Evil* —バイオハザード7レジデントイービル—
- **DIRECTOR:** Kōshi Nakanishi
- **PRODUCERS:** Masachika Kawata, Tsuyoshi Kanda
- **DEVELOPERS:** Capcom
- **PUBLISHER:** Capcom
- **GENRE:** Horror / Survival Horror
- **PLATFORMS:** PlayStation 4, Xbox One, PC — Steam—
- **RELEASE DATE:** January 26, 2017 —Japan—; January 24, 2017 —Rest of the world—
- **PRICE:** £52.95 / €59.95 / \$64.95 —PlayStation 4; £52.95 / €59.95 / \$64.95 —Xbox One; £39.95 / €44.95 / \$49.95 —PC

International cover of the PC version of *Resident Evil 7: Biohazard*

The Return of Terror to Resident Evil

Resident Evil 7: Biohazard could hardly—and should hardly—be presented without a subtitle such as this one. The use of a subtitle like *Biohazard* evokes precisely the element that long defined the series: terror. After Shinji Mikami’s shift toward a more action-oriented direction, which began with the reorientation of the franchise in the brilliant *Resident Evil 4* (2005), survival horror enthusiasts—whose understanding of the genre had been shaped by Mikami and his team at Capcom during the 1990s—no longer identified with the direction the franchise was taking.

While beloved characters continued to appear, providing fans with spectacular and sometimes epic adventures, the series' new trajectory diverged from the essence that had originally defined it. Mikami's innovative approach resulted in a phenomenal game—*Resident Evil 4*—but after his departure from Capcom, the company continued to exploit the action-oriented side of the series. Over time, this caused the franchise to lose much of its original survival horror identity.

Although *Resident Evil 5* and *Resident Evil 6* are objectively competent action games, they are far removed from the survival horror roots that long-time fans cherished. The scope of the *Resident Evil* narrative had expanded so much that it became increasingly convoluted, and along the way the tight, tense gameplay that defined the early titles under Mikami's guidance was diluted. This shortcoming is addressed in this instalment by returning to a much simpler premise. The protagonist, Ethan Winters, travels to a secluded mansion in search of his wife, who disappeared suddenly and from whom he had not heard for years. Within this confined and mysterious setting—far removed from the large-scale conflicts of previous entries—the events of the game begin to unfold.

Ethan arriving at the Baker mansion. He had no idea what horrors awaited him the moment he stepped out of his car.

When we spend the first few minutes with this new *Resident Evil*—whose subtitle, for Western audiences, finally adopts the original Japanese title *Biohazard*—we might initially think we are facing a new title by Frictional Games, perhaps another instalment in their outstanding *Amnesia* or *Penumbra* series, rather than a new *Resident Evil*. The shift to a first-person perspective, the gloomy and poorly lit environments, and the sense of vulnerability and helplessness surrounding the silent protagonist all contribute to this impression.

At first glance, many elements recall the games developed by that studio, or even the now-vanished demo *P.T.* by Kojima Productions. In terms of visual presentation—particularly the lighting and character modelling—it may also evoke memories of other notable titles such as *Alien: Isolation*, despite the obvious differences in scope and style. However, this initial impression fades once we examine *Resident Evil 7* more closely.

What becomes clear after spending a few hours with the game is that Capcom finally delivered what long-time fans of the series had been waiting for: a true return to the survival horror genre. Even the decision to control the character from a first-person perspective—though the field of view can be adjusted to make the experience more comfortable for players who find this viewpoint disorienting—proves to be an inspired choice. Interestingly, this was in fact something Shinji Mikami originally intended for the first *Resident Evil*, but which could not be realised at the time due to technical limitations.

This is particularly curious given that Mikami left Capcom, and with it the series, many years ago. Yet almost everything in this game feels like a tribute to the original titles, something that fans can only appreciate. In earlier entries in the series, enemies had to be carefully placed throughout the environments to maximise the sense of tension and surprise when they appeared. This was also achieved through the use of third-person perspectives and fixed camera angles, allowing the development team to guide the player's gaze and control what could—or could not—be seen within a given scene.

In this instalment, thanks to the use of the first-person perspective, this effect is achieved in a much more immediate and natural way, and the result is remarkably effective—especially when we consider that presenting the original *Resident Evil* game in this way was originally the creator's own intention.

The influences behind *Resident Evil 7* and its constant homages

For many critics and outlets, this title seemed to stop being a *Resident Evil* and instead became just another generic horror game. Yet such interpretations often suggest that those commentators only became familiar with the series after the 1990s. For attentive players, there is much here that unmistakably recalls the classic Capcom titles, even if influences from other franchises are also present.

From the scarcity of ammunition to the puzzles that occasionally appear—some of which feel as though they were taken straight from B-movies, such as removing an object only to trigger a trap that confines the player to the very place where it was taken—almost everything serves to open new paths through the environment. The constant stress created by apparently unstoppable enemies, the familiar structure of the exploration, and even the save rooms themselves evoke a powerful sense of nostalgia. All of these elements remain firmly within the player's reach.

Perhaps the most striking influence is the inclusion of the mansion and its surrounding environment. Visually and atmospherically, it strongly recalls *The Texas Chain Saw Massacre*, as well as the video game *Sweet Home*—particularly the scene in which a group visits a mansion, which will immediately remind players of that title, itself the original inspiration behind the *Resident Evil* series. In cinematic terms, the similarities with Tobe Hooper's *The Texas Chain Saw Massacre* are especially evident.

The presence of a grotesque family as the game's antagonists—even including a subtle homage to *Leatherface*—along with their disturbing behavioural habits and unsettling domestic environment, reinforces these parallels.

This cascade of references reaches its peak during the famous dinner scene with the Baker family—one of the sequences already shown in official previews of the game—which unmistakably echoes the iconic scene from Hooper’s film.

The well-known dinner scene with the Baker family. One of the key moments of the game, where the place Mia has gotten herself into—and the disturbing mental state of our hosts—is finally revealed with complete clarity and brutality.

Presenting the game entirely from a first-person perspective, along with the inclusion of scenes recorded by characters within the story, draws clear inspiration from films such as *REC* and *The Blair Witch Project*. In these works, the events appear to be recorded by the characters themselves, and the narrative unfolds through what is known as “found footage.” This more psychological style of horror—rather than one focused purely on spectacle and jump scares—is something from which *Resident Evil 7: Biohazard* clearly draws.

The game makes use of this technique while going a step further—into territory where cinema cannot quite follow a video game. Players actively participate in these sequences. Throughout the environments we will find several VHS tapes, and when we play them we take control of the character operating the camera. Through these segments we are able to explore areas that Ethan cannot yet access. We may even perform certain actions with these characters that could easily be overlooked, but which can provide valuable clues about the story and the setting—and may even allow us to obtain equipment that will later benefit Ethan.

We can also detect influences from the *Saw* franchise, in which a malevolent figure subjects victims to a series of cruel and elaborate tests whose outcomes rarely end well for those involved. The game features a similarly sadistic character who confronts the player with macabre trials within the environment, strongly recalling the structure and tone of those films.

Additional references can be perceived in other horror works, including games such as *Outlast* and *F.E.A.R.*—it is worth noting that one of the writers from the latter franchise contributed to this instalment of the series.

Despite these clear influences, however, we should not be misled. *Resident Evil 7* may evoke many other works, but at the same time it offers a fresh and distinctive experience. After all, the original titles in the series followed the same creative philosophy: new adventures that constantly paid homage to the horror genre and to B-movie cinema, works that felt both familiar and reminiscent of earlier fiction while still presenting something new. The series borrowed elements from other games, but always added its own distinctive touches. Players will not feel as though they are simply playing *Outlast*, and the handling of weapons in *Resident Evil 7*, along with many other design decisions, helps preserve its unique identity even when certain similarities with other works remain.

The sense of isolation characteristic of earlier horror titles—and of the classic *Resident Evil* games themselves—returns here in full force. The location to which Ethan travels is situated in the United States, yet it feels almost entirely abandoned, alienated, and cut off from the rest of the world. The Baker mansion begins to feel like an entity in its own right. In this respect, the narrative approach resembles that found in games such as *Left 4 Dead* and *Left 4 Dead 2*, or films such as *Ringu*, where atmosphere and environmental context play a crucial role in making the story believable. Certain characters even appear to echo aspects of *Ringu* in more than one respect.

The environment itself is filled with small details—decorations, scattered notes, and other subtle elements—that reveal aspects of the enemies' lives and hint at the fate of previous victims. All of these components work together to create the unsettling impression that everything surrounding the player ultimately serves the interests of the hostile forces inhabiting this place.

The game's carefully crafted atmosphere is one of its greatest strengths. Many elements within the environment convey parts of the story and its subplots, either indirectly or directly. Players can also closely examine certain objects in order to uncover clues, discover references to hidden locations, or find other items connected to the one currently being inspected.

Plot and Characters: Welcome to the Baker Family

Before continuing, I should warn the reader that I will reveal a few minor details about the plot, as well as some character names. Nothing crucial, but I will mention certain protagonists, antagonists, and supporting characters—something that might bother players who prefer to experience the game without knowing absolutely anything about its story.

In *Resident Evil 7: Biohazard* we step into the shoes of Ethan Winters. In the past, players were accustomed to controlling genuine supermen and superwomen—soldiers and highly trained operatives—who might occasionally appear vulnerable when facing overwhelming enemies, but who always gave the impression of knowing what to do, or at least of being prepared to survive in hostile environments.

This is not the case in the game before us. Ethan is an ordinary man who, after years without any news of his missing wife, decides to embark on a journey to discover what happened to her. After receiving a mysterious video message in which Mia Winters appears, he obtains clues about her whereabouts that lead him to a rural area in Dulvey, Louisiana.

In doing so, *Resident Evil 7* returns to the use of a simple narrative premise and straightforward motivations, instead of the large-scale plots and Hollywood-style spectacle that eventually came to surround the classic characters of the franchise.

The video message from Mia, which prompts Ethan to set out in search of his missing wife.

Here, the focus shifts to more intimate, straightforward storytelling and pure horror, rather than frantic action and spraying hundreds of bullets at enemies who simply drop more ammo upon defeat. Although at first glance it may seem that the story revolves around saving Mia, it's really about trying to escape the nightmare both she and Ethan are trapped in, and uncovering what happened to her during her disappearance, while Ethan himself is being hunted.

The player constantly feels that the protagonist is struggling against forces beyond his control, yet can succeed through our actions. This is where *Resident Evil 7* shines, balancing the thrill of agency—the player being able to act against the horror—with the sense of helplessness, facing overwhelming odds.

We help Ethan solve puzzles, escape encounters, and adapt as the story progresses. This is a positive feature, but it comes with drawbacks: Ethan lacks the charisma and appeal of previous franchise heroes like Chris, Claire, Jill, or Leon, speaking little and serving mainly as a vehicle for the story. Yet, his ordinariness works in favour of a more natural horror experience.

This design choice contributes significantly to the horror gameplay, paying homage to Mikami's original vision—where the player's actions could determine life or death, and survival was not guaranteed. The game often withholds explicit instructions, enhancing tension and immersion.

Ethan will try to enlist the help of a police officer, among other characters.

We are not entirely alone, however, and secondary and antagonistic characters play crucial roles. They create hope for Ethan that may or may not materialize. The Baker family, to whom Ethan travels, is bizarre and will hunt us as part of their macabre games—but they are not the only characters or environments we encounter. Other figures, such as a cautious police officer or Zoe, enrich the narrative beyond simple exploration and combat, deepening the story experience.

Characters serve both to convey the narrative and to highlight gameplay mechanics. Each primary antagonist reflects their personality in their combat or pursuit, blending gameplay and story seamlessly.

Encounters vary from one-on-one combat, ranged or melee confrontations—sometimes the game dictates the type of encounter—to fleeing through areas while avoiding enemies. Environmental hazards and traps keep players alert, as with pursuing enemies like Marguerite Baker.

Horror permeates the entire experience, but in line with the franchise's roots. Despite a more psychological and emotional tone, threats remain grounded in bioterrorism and scientific experiments rather than supernatural elements. The Baker family's sinister activities tie back to prior series concepts like Las Plagas or the T-virus. The game begins in a mansion, reminiscent of the original *Resident Evil*, though later locations expand the environment.

Ethan gradually uncovers more about his wife, but progress is neither obvious nor simple.

Jack Baker is one of those enemies we'll remember for years due to his charisma and relentless pursuit to make our lives miserable. Boss encounters may falter in some mechanics and figuring out how to overcome them, but the charisma of the various antagonists we face throughout the game cannot be denied.

He confronts the patriarch Jack, the terrifying Marguerite, the enigmatic grandmother in her rocking chair, and the obsessed Lucas with his traps. Zoe assists Ethan during his journey.

Resident Evil 7 is designed to be accessible to newcomers and series veterans alike. The story stands alone while referencing the broader franchise, though not as extensively as some fans might wish. Several endings are possible, depending on player choices.

Presentation: The Debut of RE Engine

For *Resident Evil 7*, Capcom replaced the MT Framework engine with the new RE Engine. This engine implements technologies such as chromatic aberration, film grain, lens flares, and advanced lighting effects, giving the game a visual style reminiscent of 1970s–80s horror films. Lighting and shadow usage is particularly impressive. While not the most cutting-edge graphics, they surpass many older titles in visual fidelity, recalling games like *Alien: Isolation*.

Photogrammetry enhances realism, making objects, vegetation, terrain, and character models appear natural. Every element reinforces the sense of decay and filth, particularly in the Baker mansion. Cinematic sequences contribute to immersion, simulating the perspective of characters captured on VHS tapes.

Marguerite finds Mia in one of the VHS tapes scattered throughout the game. Here, we can notice some post-processing effects that enhance the feeling of watching a hastily recorded video. Additionally, viewing the tape will assist us in our upcoming confrontation with Mrs. Baker.

The accomplished visual design is complemented by the excellent work of the game's sound team. Once again, we have a soundtrack that does not steal the spotlight, but accompanies the action and stands out at key moments. We'll also notice the inclusion of a save-theme, as in the classic Resident Evil titles.

Surround sound and the variety of audio cues we hear as we progress, along with a superb English-language voiceover, fully immerse the player in the experience. Every step we take, every door, every room or location, has ambient sound that complements both what we see and what we do not see, enhancing the feeling of solitude, anxiety, and the constant threat of an enemy lurking just around the corner... potentially targeting our protagonist.

If played using virtual reality technology, the result is a highly effective horror experience, though it may not be suitable for those prone to motion sickness from VR. The game's technical execution works in its favour, as all of its design relies on a horror experience where atmosphere and narrative, rather than jump scares, generate fear and unease—something fully reinforced by the optimal audiovisual presentation.

Regarding optimization, the game performs well on all platforms—though the Xbox One version may look slightly inferior, it still runs smoothly. However, on PC, *Resident Evil 7* truly shines, offering visual options unavailable on consoles, such as true 4K resolution, a wider sRGB colour range, different anti-aliasing modes, and smooth performance throughout, with impressively short load times for a modern game with such graphical complexity. A high-end PC is not required; if your system meets the minimum requirements, the game will run nearly flawlessly from start to finish. It is worth noting that the PC port was handled respectfully, while console versions also maintained excellent quality.

Gameplay mechanics: a new *Resident Evil* with a classic feel

At first, one might think we were facing a new *Alien: Isolation* or a new *Amnesia*. In those games, survival is paramount and often purely escapist. In *Resident Evil 7*, although the initial objective is to escape the Baker estate alive, we almost always feel that “we can fight back”—something impossible in the notable *Alien: Isolation* by Creative Assembly, where the main antagonist, the xenomorph, is invincible.

We progress through a series of levels—initially all tied to the Baker mansion—which we must explore carefully to find items for survival, craft new equipment, and solve puzzles that allow us to escape or discover new areas and secrets. While these puzzles are not as challenging or crucial as in other entries, their inclusion is appreciated and barely disrupts the game's pacing. Many fit seamlessly into the environment or reflect the mindset of our adversaries.

This is one of the game's puzzles, where we have to replace the long-awaited shotgun with a broken one—a full homage to a moment from the original *Resident Evil*.

At no point will it feel like we are trudging through endless corridors, merely advancing without thought. Areas such as the Baker mansion encourage exploration, discovery of secrets, planning attacks, and survival—fully supporting the survival horror experience. Combat emphasizes strategy, aiming at enemy weak points to conserve ammunition, a scarce resource in this game.

Controls are responsive, though we may miss guidance for certain moments or battles, sometimes forcing repeated attempts. Some enemies are indestructible and will pursue us during certain sequences, reminiscent of Nemesis from *Resident Evil 3*.

Weapons are crucial for survival, requiring careful use of ammunition. Aside from the pistol, which initially feels almost ineffective, the remaining weapons give us enough sense of power to counterbalance the protagonist's usual helplessness. However, whenever a new weapon is found, the game ensures it does not make us invincible against the dangers encountered. Unlike recent *Resident Evil* entries, combat here is less frequent but more challenging, similar to the early titles, breaking the silence during exploration and hindering progress to maintain tension.

Ethan can move on foot, crouch, or run, but his agility is limited. Hiding takes priority, and if we attack, we must aim for weak points or take enemies down one by one, or flee if we cannot defeat them—mirroring the original *Resident Evil*. The challenge comes from real combat and escape decisions, not poor control mechanics.

Safe zones allow us to save progress and store excess inventory, reminiscent of the classic typewriter rooms. In higher difficulty modes, saving may be limited, just like in classic *Resident Evil* games. The series' trademark limited inventory continues, forcing careful selection of carried items. Returning for stored items may be inconvenient or time-consuming, especially if needed for a puzzle.

As in *Resident Evil 3*, “components” appear for crafting useful gear such as ammunition. Components are scarce, forcing strategic choices between health items or ammo. Green herbs return, combinable into first aid kits, and Ethan's health is displayed via an ECG, as in the original titles, visible on his wristwatch.

For some players, all these features may seem secondary to the fundamental change: the first-person perspective. While this change also promotes VR, the game functions perfectly without it. To understand how first-person does not completely alter the experience, imagine a section in third-person and note how faithfully the franchise's principles are maintained.

Scores

- **Overall:** 87/100
- **Story:** 90/100
- **Graphics:** 95/100
- **Sound:** 85/100
- **Originality:** 70/100
- **Gameplay:** 95/100
- **Review Title:** Excellent

Conclusions

Resident Evil 7, while not the perfect survival horror game or a masterpiece, delivered what many fans had been waiting for: a breath of fresh air and a reminder that Capcom could still produce a *Resident Evil* with the virtues of the classic titles.

It successfully recaptures the franchise's essence after years of diverging entries. The game draws on familiar elements from both the Resident Evil saga and other cinematic and gaming franchises while offering a fresh, classic-feel experience. Players enjoy technically polished gameplay and strong narrative while exploring terrifying environments and uncovering the story behind them.

Sources

- **Text created by:** Andrés Domenech Alcaide [CoolJapan.es]
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